

HCl) 270, 298sh, 405; (+NaOAc) 272, 346, 382; (+NaOAc/H₃BO₃) 257, 354 mm; δ (90 MHz; DMSO-d₆) 6.25, 6.4 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz each, H-6 and H-8), 6.94 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, H-5'), 7.5 (1H, dd, *J* 2, 8 Hz, H-6'), 7.98 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, H-2'), 3.85 (3H, s, oMe), 5.82 (1H, d, *J* 6 Hz, H-1''), 4.3 (1H, s, H-1''), 3.1–4.0 (rhamnoglucosyl 10 protons) and 0.8–1.1 (1H, m, rhamnosyl methyl).

The chemical degradations of the glycoside were made by the reported methods⁶. It revealed the presence of Rutinosyl moiety at position-3, which was also supported by the anomeric proton signals at δ 5.82 (diaxial coupling) and the rest of the sugar portion at δ 4.3 and 0.8–1.1 (m) in its pmr spectrum. The aglycone (obtained by its acidic hydrolysis), m.p. 304–06°, C₁₆H₁₂O₇, *M*⁺ 316, was confirmed as isorhamnetin by comparing its uv, pmr and mass spectral data⁷.

The compound was thus assigned as isorhamnetin 3-*O*-rutinoside which is comparatively rare in nature and is being reported for the first time in Myrtaceae family. Its occurrence is of good taxonomic interest and owing to the vast structural variation among the anthoxanthins, throws light towards the direction of secondary metabolites.

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2-Hydroxy-1-acetonaphthoneoxime as an Analytical Reagent for Spectrophotometric Determination of Iron(III) and Fluoride†

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2-Hydroxy-1-acetonaphthoneoxime (2-HANO) has been found to give a greenish violet complex with iron(III) of 1 : 2 (metal-ligand) composition which absorbs maximally at 600 nm, the absorbance maximum of the reagent alone being 320 nm. This colour reaction has been used for the determination of iron(III), and indirectly for fluoride.

Experimental

Preparation of reagent: 2-Naphthol was converted into 2-naphthyl acetate by treating it with acetic anhydride¹. This compound was subjected to Fric's rearrangement²⁻⁴ as recommended by Joshi and Shah⁴ and the resulting mixture was steam-distilled when 2-hydroxy-1-acetonaphthone was obtained in good yield. The oxime of this compound was prepared by refluxing the ketone with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in the presence of sodium acetate.

Preparation of 1-HANO: The first step, i.e. preparation of 2-acetyl-1-naphthol was conducted by the use of Nencki reaction with 1-naphthol⁵, and the reported oxime of the ketone was prepared according to the reported procedure⁶.

All the reagents were of AnalaR grade. Stock solution of iron(III) (1 mg ml⁻¹) was prepared by dissolving ammonium ferric sulphate in distilled water.

Stock solution of fluoride (1 mg ml⁻¹) was prepared from sodium fluoride. Sulphuric acid (0.05 *M*) was used to maintain the pH.

A Shimadzu UV-240 spectrophotometer was used for measuring absorbance. pH was measured using an Elico pH meter.

Determination of iron(III): Aliquots of iron(III) (1–50 μ g) and 2-HANO (0.025 *M*; 5 ml) were mixed and shaken well. To it sulphuric acid (0.05 *M*; 10 ml) was added and the solution was made upto 25 ml with distilled water, the final pH being 3.5. The absorbance of solutions was measured after 10 min at 600 nm against the reagent blank.

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Determination of fluoride: Aliquots of iron(III) (0.0025 M; 4 ml), 2-HANO (0.025 M; 4 ml) and sulphuric acid (0.05 M; 10 ml) were mixed and shaken well. Aliquots of fluoride (1–20 μg) were then added to the complex and the solution was made upto 25 ml mark with distilled water. After 15 min the absorbance of the solutions was measured at 600 nm against the reagent blank.

We reported⁷ earlier that 1-HANO formed a greenish violet 1:1 complex with iron(III) in the pH range 2.0–4.0. We now report the use of this complex as well for the determination of fluoride.

Aliquots of iron(III) (0.0025 M; 2 ml), 1-HANO (0.025 M; 2 ml) and sulphuric acid (0.05 M; 10 ml) were mixed and shaken well. Aliquots of fluoride (1–20 μg) were then added to the complex and the contents made up to the 25 ml with 95% ethanol (v/v). The absorbance of the solutions was measured at 640 nm after 15 min against the reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

The basis of the estimation of iron(III) is the formation of intense greenish violet coloured complex by 2-HANO with iron(III). The results reveal that in the presence of five-fold excess of the reagent the iron(III)-2-HANO complex obeyed Beer's law in the range 1–18 μg of iron(III) in 25 ml.

Studies made using Job's mole-ratio, slope-ratio and Ausmus methods indicate that 2-HANO forms a 1:2 (metal-ligand) complex with iron(III). The Sandell's sensitivity and molar absorptivity were found to be 0.046 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and $4.0 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. Identification limit and dilution limit were found to be 0.46 μg and $1:14.9 \times 10^3$ respectively. The stability constant of the complex determined by Ausmus method was found to be 6.25×10^8 . Diverse ions such as Fe^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Ag^{+} , Be^{2+} , La^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , UO_2^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{3+} , Mn^{2+} , Pd^{2+} , chloride, bromide, iodide, carbonate, sulphite, sulphate, acetate do not interfere even when present in ten-fold excess to iron(III). More than 0.5 ppm of V^{5+} , Ti^{4+} and Cu^{2+} interfere under the experimental conditions. Fluoride and phosphate seriously interfere at all levels.

Fluoride was estimated based on the principle that it reacts with iron(III) to form a complex which is stronger than the iron(III) complex with the reagent. A plot of ΔA vs concentration of fluoride, indicates that amounts of fluoride in the range 1–9 μg in 25 ml could be determined by using iron(III)-2-HANO complex and 2–9 μg in 25 ml could be determined using iron(III)-1-HANO complex.

The accuracy is comparable to that of the standard procedure using SPADNS reagent⁸ for

the determination of fluoride. The standard deviation is 0.00326 and 0.00554 for 1-HANO and 2-HANO systems respectively. Moreover, the reagent could be easily prepared.

The metals like Th^{4+} , Zr^{4+} , Be^{2+} , B^{3+} , V^{5+} , Cu^{2+} , Ti^{4+} , Sr^{2+} and Ce^{2+} seriously interfere in both the methods for the estimation of fluoride.

2-HANO reacts with iron(III) only in acidic pH, the reaction being unaffected by the presence of iron(II). Thus the reagent is useful to determine iron(III) in the presence of iron(II) for which very few reagents qualify.

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Extraction Photo metric Determination of Microgram Amounts of Cobalt with Thiocyanate and Cetyltrimethylammonium Bromide

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THE thiocyanate complex of cobalt, which is not extractable into chloroform, readily forms extractable ion-pair with the quaternary ammonium ion derived from cetyltrimethylammonium bromide. Measurement of absorbance of this extract forms the basis of the present method for the estimation of μg amounts of cobalt.

Experimental

Cobalt solution was prepared from $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and standardised. Solutions of 0.2 M